

DIGITAL-BASED TEACHING MATERIALS WITH CLIL ENHANCE MOTHER TONGUE LANGUAGE SKILL (LANGUAGE USE)

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Abstract

This research aims to produce a product in the form of a model of regional language teaching materials (Job Using) with a digital-based CLIL approach that is feasible and effective for elementary school students. The research was conducted in 2020-2023 on elementary school students at SDN Model Banyuwangi, East Java, Indonesia. Data was collected through interviews, questionnaires and tests. The results of trials and data processing show a significant increase; based on the Paired T-Test test, the significance value was 0.000 ($p < 0.05$), with the conclusion that the Using language teaching material model with a digital-based CLIL approach was effectively used in improving the language skills of elementary school students. The gap in regional language learning as an effort to maintain a language and the lack of availability of teaching materials (Work Using) answers the needs experienced by teachers and students.

Keywords: Digital, Language Teaching Materials, CLIL Approach.

1. INTRODUCTION

Regional language learning still attracts much attention as an effort to maintain the mother tongue Botifar et al. (2020); Harwati (2018); Dolphen (2014); Yan et al. (2010); Kafata (2016). In Indonesia, Banyuwangi East Java is located and is used for regional language learning in elementary schools. PlearningWork Using started in 1990 (Tyasari et al., 2017). Based on Law Number 20 of 2003, the use of regional languages is mandatory in the implementation of national education in Indonesia. The policy regarding the implementation of using language at the elementary school education level in Banyuwangi is stated in number 1702/104/94/SK of 2003, and Permendiknas number 22 of 2006 that learning the Using language at elementary school and madrasa level in Banyuwangi district must be given to students (Jayanti, 2022).

CLIL or content and language integrated learning, is designed for various subjects for students using a foreign language. The CLIL approach in language learning is quite widely used. Morikoshi et al. (2018) discuss the design of textbooks with CLIL by integrating material, thinking, knowledge and use of language, teaching and learning, and cross-cultural understanding into the classroom. CLIL is used in learning as an effort to motivate students to learn languages. The results of the CLIL approach are better than those of conventional approaches. Namely, it is able to create an effective learning process for speaking skills (Mede & Cinar, 2018). Several studies using the CLIL approach (2008-2018) also show a positive impact on the development of student's abilities and skills. This combination of content and language teaching is implemented in bilingual education programs (bilingual education) found in America (Banegas et al., 2020). Tomlinson (2001) stated that language teaching materials should be able to facilitate language learning, whether linguistic, visual, auditory, or kinesthetic, and they can be presented in print or non-print form with the help of the internet. Digital teaching materials are one of the innovations in information and communication technology in the world of education, which can make information

media in learning more interactive and more interesting, and the time used is more flexible so that it can be done anywhere and at any time (Wright, 2017). Schunk (2015) stated that teaching materials combined with digital or other multimedia devices, such as interactive two-dimensional image displays and audio and video visual forms, will create interesting learning for students. Şanlıtürk & Zeybek (2022) confirmed in their research that digital teaching materials featuring cartoon concepts are highly effective in enhancing student participation in the learning process.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Language Teaching Materials and CLIL Theory

Tomlinson's (2008) teaching materials refer to everything used by teachers and students in language learning. Rowntree (1996) stated that teaching materials should function as independent learning for teachers and students and should be developed to complement audio, video, and computer programs. Bao (2013) develops speaking teaching materials that must be oriented to students' needs without looking at their current and future needs. Meanwhile, in the listening process, a person not only listens to sounds, but it is also a more intense listening activity to understand the meaning of the communication conveyed by the speaker (Iskandarwassid & Sunendar, 2011).

Nunan (2003) stated that reading activity is a process that combines information from the text with the knowledge possessed by the reader to build meaning. Chen and Chia-li (2015) state that reading is a complex interactive cognitive process that extracts meaning from text. Through this reading process, the reader becomes an active participant who constructs meaning from the instructions in the reading text. Reading skills are not specific abilities but are general abilities that include comprehensive cognitive processes. One of the comprehensive cognitive processes that readers must have is through prior knowledge (García et al., 2017). Kong (2019) states that reading skills can be carried out through four interrelated cycles that appear sequentially. Writing skills should balance students' reading needs in the real world with the writing activities they need in class or during exams (Hyland, 2013). Tribble's (2010) writing needs include knowledge of the material, context, language system, and knowledge of writing activities. CLIL has been developed for several decades in several parts of the world, including Europe, Asia, Canada and the United States, which has been proven and is quite recognized in language learning (Pablo & Jimenez, 2018). CLIL is an approach to learning that focuses on school subjects to be taught and learned through a second language (Urmeneta, 2019). Furthermore, Kováčiková (2020), in the CLIL approach, emphasizes the process of children's mental development, such as memory, attention, and reasoning, which involves learning using community findings such as language and memory tools. Morikoshi et al. (2018) integrated the 4Cs viz Content, Cognition, Communication and Culture into class and how to process activities in class, such as pair work, group discussions and exercises online used in CLIL learning.

For Coyle, Hood, and Marsh, the CLIL approach is considered appropriate for understanding the subject matter being taught as well as deepening the language used in learning. In this case, a foreign language or second language is used as a tool in studying non-language subjects where the language and subject have shared roles (Coyle et al., 2010). Next, they demonstrated learning with the CLIL approach as follows:

Figure 1: CLIL Approach in Learning

Šulistová (2015) gives advantages of the use of content and Language Integrated Learning, including a) a learning process based on everyday life; b) allows students to have more contact with the target language; 3) improved language competence and oral communication skills; and 4) acquire communicative skills. However, from the advantages, there are disadvantages to using content and Language Integrated Learning. These are 1) high consumption for the preparation of ingredients; 2) students or teachers do not have foreign language skills relevant to the content; 3) insufficient information about CLIL methods; 4) lack of motivation to use the CLIL approach; and 5) there is reluctance regarding training regarding CLIL.

The essential thing that can be taken from the explanation above is that learning uses an approach called content and language-integrated learning, which is an approach that combines language learning and the language used in learning without leaving out cultural aspects as part of the integration of learning. So even in this research, for using language subjects as local content, students learn themes through using language. Thus, the content studied is subject themes, and the language used to study the content is Using language.

2.2 Digital-Based Language Teaching Materials

Sadjati (2012) states that the existence of good teaching materials will be beneficial for both teachers and students; students can study the material to be taught first so that the remaining time can be used for discussions, questions and answers, or other learning activities, improving the learning process to be more effective and interactive. Madya (2003) states that a person's goal in learning a language is to master the language as a communication system so that in the communicative approach, linguistic skills and communicative abilities should be linked to each other. Bahman (1990) states that the aim of learning a language is to master language skills as a means of communication; this is known as CLA or communicative competence (Richards, 2006). For Richards, the communicative competence that is expected to emerge in students is being able to understand how to use language for various functions and purposes, as well as understanding how to use language well with interlocutors, various kinds of texts and being able to produce them, and being able to

maintain continuity of communication even though experiencing various kinds of difficulties and difficulties obstacle.

Rosenberg (2001) uses internet technology to distribute learning materials so that students can access them from anywhere and at any time. Digital teaching materials can also be interpreted as delivering learning material via the internet, smartphones, and other media that can be done both in the classroom and outside the classroom (Ruggeri et al., 2013; Frehywot et al., & Ruiz, 2006). Munir (2009) uses digital technology in the learning process, which has several benefits. Students communicate easily and quickly, making students more active in studying learning material, acquiring knowledge or information independently, not relying on gifts from the teacher, adjusted to their desires and interests in the learning material. Putra, Yulianti, & Fitriawan (2023) is available as a flipbook digital, which can convert files into format flash flipping books. This digital book can manage teaching materials that are interesting for students because it has the advantage of being able to enable students to adjust existing navigation buttons such as displaying music, quizzes, images and videos. Flipbook Digital, which is not only limited to text but can also include images, animation, video and audio, will make it more interactive so that learning materials are easily accessible at low cost (Candra & Susilo Wibowo, 2021; Nurhayati et al., 2021).

Kier and Khalil (2018) suggest that a creative and innovative teacher must be able to develop teaching materials in digital format as a learning medium that can create an interesting and conducive learning atmosphere. Furthermore, Ameriza (2021) flipbook digital has the ability to be used online and offline (from soft copy) and can be accessed on both laptops and smartphones, making it highly suitable for educational development both in school and at home as an alternative learning medium. Afwan (2020) also states that Flipbook Digital is a form of interactive learning media. Apart from that, the use of flipbooks can improve student learning outcomes by utilizing text, audio and visual content (Zulhelmi, 2021).

Furie & Cox's (2013) app flipbook has been used worldwide to develop teaching materials as a learning strategy that can support active learning without space and time constraints. This innovation can be an interactive educational tool via cell phones and computers (Bringman-Rodenbarger & Hortsch, 2020). Apart from being beneficial for students, flipbooks are also beneficial for teachers who give freedom in their teaching, whether to use electronic learning materials or not. In this case, students are not obligated or necessary to access electronic learning materials. The aim is to provide additional knowledge regarding learning materials. Development of teaching materials by utilizing flipbook applications has become one of the appropriate media for managing teaching materials that are attractive to students (Mutia & Emilia, 2022).

Based on its form, this digital-based language teaching material for grade 5 students is technology-based (Amri et al., 2023). It includes interactive teaching materials, namely teaching materials that combine two or more media interactively, such as audio, text, images and video media. To use this teaching material, you need tools such as a computer or smartphone, while the application used in making digital-based language teaching materials is using Heyzine flipbook.

Dewantara (2018) explains that Heyzine flipbook is an online website for converting PDF flipbooks by providing an electronic book effect that can be opened on each page like a book. Advantages of module flipbook: Some material elements can be made

interesting, such as videos, songs, audio, animation or moving graphics, which can be integrated into teaching materials. Using the application flipbook, this book is produced in digital format, making it easy for students to access language learning materials wherever and whenever they want. Here is the main viewHeyzine.com flipbook, which works to insert files into Word documents such as PDF, video, image, YouTube videos, sounds, and clipart, and add effects to each page of teaching materials.

3. METHODS

This type of research is research and development to develop teaching material products that adopt the development steps of Dick, Carey, & Carey (2015). For Airasian (2012), the purpose of development research in education is not only to formulate or test theories but to develop effective products for use in schools. This research was carried out at SDN Model Banyuwangi; geographically, the school is in the middle of the city and has varied teacher and student backgrounds. Respondent selection uses purposive random sampling techniques by paying attention to the characteristics of teachers and students at school. Apart from that, the SDN Model is also an elementary school with a language curriculum. Initial observations were carried out to identify the curriculum and teaching materials for Using the language currently used and the needs of students and teachers for teaching Using language; small class tests were carried out in class 5 with the consideration that the class already knew and implemented the local content of Using language.

The research was carried out from March 2020 until completion. The following is a table of activities carried out. The approach used is combined research (mixed method). At the same time, qualitative data analysis techniques include data related to 1) Information about Using language teaching materials used by students and teachers, 2) Input, responses and suggestions from designing models of Using language teaching materials, 3) Information from test respondents try first, 4) Input from the teacher regarding the teaching materials and syllabus being developed.

Quantitative data was obtained through a questionnaire analyzing teacher, and student needs to be related to the teaching material products to be developed. Product assessment questionnaires were conducted by experts, who were described in percentages and then explained qualitatively. The effectiveness test was carried out using experimental research methods in the form of Pre-Experimental Design. The techniques used are one-group pretest and posttest design. In testing the effectiveness of teaching materials, homogeneity tests, normality tests and t-tests are carried out on students' pretest and posttest scores.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After carrying out a series of studies such as reviewing expert tests, teacher and student perception tests (small group tests), the researchers then tested the effectiveness of the model by conducting experiments or trials on large groups of students in classes 5A and 5B at the Banyuwangi Model State Elementary School. The average age of students is 11 years old, and comes from the same ethnicity and environment. Students' abilities are in the average range; the averages show this for classes 5A and 5B, which tend to be the same. The effectiveness test was carried out using experimental research methods in the form of Pre-Experimental Design. The technique used is the One-Group Pretest-Posttest Design. Plan One-Group Pretest-

Posttest Design This uses an experimental group by giving two tests, namely a pretest, carried out before treatment, and a posttest, carried out after treatment (Sugiyono, 2012).

The effectiveness test was carried out for four weeks from 2 - 28 October 2023, namely 1 (one) meeting for observation and conducting a pretest, treatment was carried out 6 (six) meetings, and posttest was carried out 1 (one) meeting. The first large group trial was conducted on 12 students, while the second was on 11. The following is the distribution of research respondents.

Table 1. Distribution of Research Respondents

Class	Male	Female	Total
V-A	7	5	12
V-B	5	6	11

Based on the table above, the number of male respondents was 10 students with a percentage of 43.47%. Meanwhile, there were 13 female respondents or 56.53% of students. Thus, the students who were respondents did not have significant diversity. The effectiveness test was carried out to determine the difference in average scores before and after using teaching materials. The questions given to measure these differences were 15 questions consisting of 5 questions for verbal communication skills, 5 questions for reading skills, and 5 questions for writing skills and had received input from the teacher.

4.1 Class 5A Effectiveness Test at SDN Model Banyuwangi

Table 2: Highest Score, Lowest Score and Average Test Results for Class 5A

		Pretest 5A	Posttest 5A
N	Valid	12	12
	Missing	12	12
Mean		65.00	78.33
Median		62.00	75.00
Mode		72	72
Std. Deviation		9.890	10.714
Variance		97.818	114.788
Range		28	30
Minimum		52	66
Maximum		80	96

Based on the results of the pretest carried out before treatment, the lowest score for class 5A at SDN Model was 52, the highest score was 80, with an average score of 65.00. Then the results of the posttest carried out after the treatment produced the lowest score of 66, the highest score was 96, with an average score of 78.33.

The normality test is carried out to determine that the data that has been collected is taken from a normal population. Because the sample size was small, data normality was detected using the Shapiro Wilk technique.

The hypothesis to be tested is H0 if the probability is > 0.05 then the population is normally distributed (H0 is accepted), while H1 if the probability is < 0.05 then the population is not normally distributed (H0 is rejected). The output table for the Shapiro Wilk normality test is in "Test of Normality" as follows:

Table 3: Data Normality Test for Class 5A Trial Results

Tests of Normality								
		KEL5A	Kolmogorov-Smirnov			Shapiro-Wilk		
			Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Class 5A Learning Results	1	.255	12	.060	.893	12	.128	
	2	.223	12	.103	.883	12	.095	

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Based on the table above, df (degrees of freedom) or data samples were taken from 12 students. It is known that the sig value for the pretest group is 0.128 and the sig value for the posttest group is 0.95. Because the sig value for the two groups above is > 0.05 , it can be concluded that the pretest and posttest value data are normally distributed.

Table 4: Data Homogeneity Test for Class 5A Trial Results

Test of Homogeneity of Variances					
		Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
Class 5A Learning Results	Based on Mean	.169	1	22	.685
	Based on Median	.309	1	22	.584
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	.309	1	21.983	.584
	Based on trimmed mean	.149	1	22	.704

The homogeneity test is carried out to test whether the data has the same diversity of values. This test is used to ensure that the data group comes from the same sample. The test is said to be homogeneous based on its significance value. If the significance value (Sig) > 0.05 indicates the data group comes from a population that has the same variance (homogeneous), while if the significance value (Sig) < 0.05 indicates each data group comes from a population with a different variance (not homogeneous). The test results produced Sig data of 0.685. The Sig value is $0.685 > 0.05$, so as is the basis for decision making in the homogeneity test above, it is concluded that the variances are the same or homogeneous.

Table 5: Paired Sample T Test on Class 5A Trial Results Data

Paired Samples Test									
		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	Pretest 5A - Posttest 5A	-13.333	2.995	.865	-15.236	-11.430	-15.422	11	.000

The test was continued with the Paired Sample T Test to measure the difference in the two averages between the pretest and post-test. Paired Sample t-test is a test used to compare the difference between two means from two paired samples with the assumption that the data is usually distributed. Paired samples come from the same subject, and each variable is taken in different situations and circumstances.

The test is carried out if the significance value (2-tailed) is < 0.05 , meaning it shows a significant difference between the initial and final variables. This significantly influences the differences in treatment given to each variable. Meanwhile, if the significance value (2-tailed) is > 0.05 , there is no significant difference between the

initial and final variables. This shows no significant influence on the differences in treatment given to each variable.

Significance value (2-tailed) from example Table 4.31. Is 0.000 ($p < 0.05$). Thus, the pretest and post-test results experienced significant changes. Thus, using the language teaching material model with a digital-based CLIL approach, tested on class 5A students, effectively improves students' language skills.

4.2 Class 5B Effectiveness Test at SDN Model Banyuwangi

Table 6: Highest Score, Lowest Score and Average Class 5B Test Results

		Posttest5B	Pretest 5B
N	Valid	11	11
	Missing	13	13
Mean		72.55	63.27
Median		72.00	64.00
Mode		72	58 ^a
Std. Deviation		6.138	5.815
Variance		37.673	33.818
Range		24	18
Minimum		60	52
Maximum		84	70
a. Multiple modes exist. The smallest value is shown			

Based on the results of the pretest carried out before treatment, the lowest score for class 5B at SDN Model was 52, the highest score was 70, with an average score of 63.27. Then the results of the posttest carried out after the treatment produced the lowest score of 60, the highest score was 84, with an average score of 72.55.

The normality test is carried out to determine that the data that has been collected is taken from a normal population. Because the sample size was small, data normality was detected using the Shapiro Wilk technique. The hypothesis to be tested is H0 if the probability is > 0.05 then the population is normally distributed (H0 is accepted), while H1 if the probability is < 0.05 then the population is not normally distributed (H0 is rejected). The Shapiro Wilk normality test output table is in "Test of Normality" as follows:

Table 7: Data Normality Test for Class 5B Trial Results

Tests of Normality							
	KEL5B	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Class 5 B Learning Results	1	.155	11	.200*	.931	11	.421
	2	.225	11	.127	.919	11	.312
*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.							
a. Lilliefors Significance Correction							

Based on the table above, df (degrees of freedom) or data samples were taken from 11 students. It is known that the sig value for the pretest group is 0.421 and the sig value for the posttest group is 0.312. Because the sig value for the two groups above is > 0.05 , it can be concluded that the pretest and posttest value data are normally distributed.

Table 8: Data Homogeneity Test for Class 5B Trial Results

Test of Homogeneity of Variances					
		Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
Class 5 B Learning Results	Based on Mean	.008	1	14	.929
	Based on Median	.000	1	14	1.000
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	.000	1	13.214	1.000
	Based on trimmed mean	.003	1	14	.954

The homogeneity test is carried out to test whether the data has the same diversity of values. This test is used to ensure that the data group comes from the same sample.

The test is said to be homogeneous based on its significance value. If the significance value (Sig) > 0.05 indicates the data group comes from a population that has the same variance (homogeneous), while if the significance value (Sig) < 0.05 indicates each data group comes from a population with a different variance (not homogeneous).

The test results produced Sig data of 0.929. The Sig value is 0.929 > 0.05, so as the basis for decision making in the homogeneity test above, it is concluded that the variances are the same or homogeneous.

Table 9: Paired Sample T Test on Class 5B Trial Results Data

Paired Samples Test		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	Pretest 5B - Posttest5B	-9.273	5.159	1.556	-12.739	-5.807	-5.961	10	.000

The test was continued with the Paired Sample T Test to measure the difference in the two averages between the pretest and post-test. Paired Sample t-test is a test used to compare the difference between two means from two paired samples with the assumption that the data is usually distributed. Paired samples come from the same subject, and each variable is taken in different situations and circumstances.

The test is carried out if the significance value (2-tailed) is <0.05, meaning it shows a significant difference between the initial and final variables. This significantly influences the differences in treatment given to each variable. Meanwhile, if the significance value (2-tailed) is > 0.05, there is no significant difference between the initial and final variables. This shows no significant influence on the differences in treatment given to each variable.

The significance value (2-tailed) is 0.000 ($p < 0.05$). Thus, the pretest and post-test results experienced significant changes. Thus, it can be concluded that the Using language teaching material model with a digital-based CLIL approach, tested on class 5B students, effectively improves students' native language skills in Using Language.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Test the effectiveness of the teaching material model developed. The effectiveness test results show a significant increase based on the Paired T-Test test. The significance value obtained at SDN Model Banyuwangi is for the VA class; the statistical data obtained is $t = 15.422$ with $df = 11$, and the number sig. or p-value = 0.000 ($p < 0.05$) or H_0 is rejected. Meanwhile, for class, VB, $t = 5,961$ with $df = 10$ and the number sig. or p-value ($p < 0.05$) or H_0 is rejected. So it can be concluded that there are differences between the pretest and post-test using language teaching materials, which means a model of Using language teaching materials with an approach content and language-integrated learning Digital-based (CLIL) is efficacious in improving the language skills of class V students at SDN Model Banyuwangi. This can be seen from the results of the pretest speaking skills of class 5 students who can use vocabulary selection and articulation or pronunciation in Work Using according to the theme being taught.

Suggestions for models of Using language teaching materials with approaches content and language integrated learning Digital-based (CLIL) was developed through a series of systematic research and can be used as a reference for preparing teaching materials and learning plans that meet the requirements. In developing teaching materials designed for use in schools, the government, as an education provider, needs to carry out feasibility tests on teaching materials that will be used for product development.

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